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Effect of Job Motivation on Cooperative Society and Members' Performance Output in Ogun State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigated the effect of job motivation on cooperative society and members' performance output in Ogun State, Nigeria. A total of one hundred and twenty (120) respondents were selected using cluster sampling technique and interviewed through well-structured questionnaire. Descriptive statistics such as frequency table, measure of central tendency and percentages were used and the regression model was used to analyse the impact of cooperative services on members' outputs. The results revealed on socio-economic characteristics of the cooperative members revealed even distribution of the respondents with both male and females accounted for in this study. It was noted from the study that the average age of the respondents was 40.16 years. A good number of them (40.8%) attended secondary school. Education, in this study meant the ability to read and write. Majority (45.8%) were traders and majority (65.0%) of the cooperatives members are under the Credit and Thrift Cooperative Societies. The study further revealed that majority of the cooperative societies (50.8%) were offering all type of services from marketing to credit facilities to their members and 53.3% of the cooperative societies were serving a range of multipurpose from marketing, to credit and procurement of inputs purposes. The relationships with peers, assistance from the government and any other bodies, number in the management team, staff training/development programs, working conditions and promotion in the organization all motivates cooperative performance in the study area. Credit and household size are needed more to enhance cooperative members' output. Challenges militating against the cooperative societies in rendering services to cooperative members are inadequate capitalization, high cost of obtaining farm inputs, inadequate infrastructure and inadequate capacity building/training. It was therefore recommended that people should be encouraged and enlightened to form and join cooperative society. The ministry responsible for cooperative should give reorientation to people on the benefits and need of obtaining cooperative membership, which will enable them access credit to increase output.

Keywords: Effect, Job Motivation, Cooperative Society, Abeokuta South, Nigeri

INTRODUCTION

All organizations want to be successful, even in current environment which is highly competitive. Therefore, companies irrespective of size and market strive to retain the best employees, acknowledging their

important role and influence on organizational effectiveness. In order to overcome these challenges, companies should create a strong and positive relationship with its employees and direct them towards task fulfillment (Ovidiu-Iliuta, 2013). In order to achieve their goals and objectives, organizations develop strategies to compete in highly competitive markets and to increase their performance. Nevertheless, just a few organizations consider the human capital as being their main asset, capable of leading them to success or if not managed properly, to decline. If the employees are not satisfied with their jobs and not motivated to fulfill their tasks and achieve their goals, the organization cannot attain success.

People have many needs that are continuously competing one with another. Each person has a different mixture and strength of needs, as some people are driven by achievement while others are focusing on security (Ovidiu-Iliuta, 2013). If the managers are able to understand, predict and control employee behavior, they should also know what the employees want from their jobs. Therefore, it is essential for a manager to understand what really motivates employees, without making just an assumption. Asking an employee how he feels about a particular situation does not provide an accurate evaluation of his needs, as the interpretation could distort the reality itself.

Psychologists are intrigued by human motivation and many of the motivational theories developed in the last century are applicable today. Use of the theories has enabled us to understand the link between motivation and job satisfaction, productivity, leadership styles and personal characteristics. There is a general belief that man has the natural tendency to be lazy with regards to work and he is being forced by circumstances to work. This idea about man still continues to create problems for the development process of the society in the face of abundant human and material resources resulting to low productivity (Srivastava and Barmola, 2011). Low productivity is a problem that thrives in many societies particularly in the developing countries irrespective of constant efforts.

Motivation is the willingness to perform certain tasks due to rewards or benefits which are attached to the performance of the tasks. Motivation is the interest of an individual or an employee to achieve a given goal. It can also be regarded as the need in a human being which creates a vacuum in that person. In an attempt to fill the vacuum, an internal driving force is generated which starts and sustains a chain of action and reaction leading to the filling of the vacuum. With this background information, Akindede (2003) defined employees' motivation as the internal or external driving force that produces the willingness to perform an act to a conclusive end. This first aspect of motivation is described as internal motivation because the driving force comes from within an individual. The second aspect is external motivation which comes from payment of salaries and other incentives provided to employees in an organization. Citizens of this country, mostly the employed people go to work in order to receive payment from employees to keep life going. The extent to which we work hard in our employment to receive our monthly salary is determined by the level of motivation from our employer.

Performance is an evaluation of the results of a person's behaviour. It involves determining how well or poorly a person has accomplished a task or done a job. Motivation is only one factor among many that contributes to an employee's job performance. All things being equal, one would expect a highly motivated teacher or an officer would deliver high-quality teaching or service than those poorly motivated teacher or officer. All things however, are not always equal because so many factors affect performance factors such as personality, the difficulty of the task, availability of resources and working conditions (Boamah, 2014). To attain high levels of performance as an employee and manager, you must be sure that you and your employees have the ability, motivation and the resources to meet objectives. When performance is not at the standard level or above, you must determine which performance factor needs to be improved and improve it (Lussier, 2005).

The original impetus for the introduction of cooperative in Nigeria came from agriculture, or more precisely the marketing of cash crops for export. This development no doubt could be as a result of the inherent potential in cooperative as observed in other parts of the world. Amar (2004) stated that in consideration of the impact of cooperative society in agricultural production in developed economics, farmers in developing countries had been encouraged to organize themselves into cooperative societies. As noted earlier not many

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farmers have embraced the organizational form to make it work for them. Yet the advantages of belonging to farmers' cooperative abound. According to Chambo (2009), agricultural cooperative create the ability for the supply of required agricultural inputs so that production of commodities is done timely to enhance productivity. They also provide an assured market for commodities produced by isolated small farmers in the rural areas. Ortman and King (2006) stated that with collective action, agricultural cooperatives can capture the benefits of value added, because of bulking and take advantages of introducing grades and standards thereby allowing agro processing value addition for the members. In addition, agricultural cooperatives are responsible for stimulating poor farmers to make entry into markets, enhancing demand for standards and grades for perishable commodities, such as bananas, onions and tomatoes.

As a development tool, successive Nigerian governments at Federal and State levels had used cooperative as platform for delivering their agricultural and rural development policies. Some of such programmes include: Family Economic Advancement Programme (FEAP); Agricultural Credit Support Scheme (ACSS); National Agricultural Land Development Authority (NALDA). Currently, the ACSS, Agricultural Input Delivery Scheme (fertilizer, seedling, breeding stock), National Poverty Eradication Programme (NAPEP) and institutional credit supports such as Microfinance Banks (MFBs), have majorly built in the vehicular tool of cooperative societies (Uneze and Onugu, 2012). Hence, need to rediscover the cooperative advantage to help improve the income and productivity of the rural farmers. According to Ibe (2002), cooperative society has been identified as the appropriate vehicle for harnessing and pooling the resources of millions of desperate producers together to enjoy the benefit of large-scale production. It is the intention of this work to rediscover and highlight these benefits so that non-cooperative, small scale rural farmers will embrace them and make it work for them.

Objectives of the study

The main objective of the study is to assess the effect of job motivation on cooperative society and members' performance output in Ogun State, Nigeria. The specific objectives are to:

- i. describe the socio-economic characteristics of the farmers;
- ii. determine the effect of motivation on employee performance;
- iii. determine the impact of cooperative services on members' outputs;
- iv. identify the challenges militating against cooperatives in rendering these services to members.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Study Area

Study Area

The study area is **Ogun** State, western Nigeria. It was created in 1976 and comprising former Abeokuta and Ijebu provinces of former Western State, the latter carved out of former Western Region in 1967. Ogun is bounded by Oyo and Osun States to the north, Lagos State to the south, Ondo State to the east, and the Republic of Benin to the west. It is covered predominantly by tropical rain forest and has wooded savanna in the northwest.

Agriculture, the economic mainstay of Ogun, produces rice, corn (maize), cassava (manioc), yams, plantains, and bananas. Cocoa, kola nuts, rubber, palm oil and palm kernels, tobacco, cotton, and timber are the main cash crops. The Aro granite quarries near Abeokuta, the state capital, provide building material for much of southern Nigeria. Mineral resources include limestone, chalk, phosphates, and clay. Industries produce cement, canned foods, foam rubber, paint, tires, carpets, aluminum products, and plastics. Abeokuta, an important market centre, is a terminus of the roads and railways coming from Lagos and other parts of the country. Major tourist attractions are Olumo rock, which according to tradition provided refuge for early Egba settlers; the Ake, the residence of the *alake* (the traditional ruler of Egbaland), built in 1854 and noted for its collection of antiquities and relics; and the Centenary Hall, all in Abeokuta.

Figure 1: Map of Ogun State showing the study area

Method of Data Collection

Both primary and secondary data were collected and used for the study. The primary data were collected through the use of well-structured questionnaire and interview schedule while the secondary data were sourced from textbooks, journals and other relevant sources.

Sampling Technique

From clusters of cooperative societies in Ogun State, the 12 cooperative societies chosen were from the study area. A total of ten (10) respondents were selected from each of the society making a total of one hundred twenty (120) respondents to be sampled.

Methods of Data Analysis

(i) Socio-Economic Characteristics of the Respondents

Descriptive statistics such as mean, frequency counts and charts were used to describe the socio economic characteristics of the respondents in the study area.

(ii) Effect of Motivation on Cooperative Performance

The effect of motivation on cooperative performance was measured using a profile of perceptual statements that was presented to the farmers on a 5 point Likert-type scale of Very high, High, Uncertain, Low and Very low. The score for individual cooperators was computed. Using mean score of all the cooperators, those having scores that equals the mean score or above were regarded as having a high effect, while those having scores below the mean score were regarded as having a low effect.

(iii) Impact of Cooperative Services on Members’ Outputs

The multiple regression analysis was used to analyse the impact of cooperative services on members’ outputs. Regression model is specified thus:

$$Y = f (X_1, X_2, X_3, X_4, X_5, X_6, X_7, X_8).....(1)$$

Where:

- Y = Value of members' output (naira)
- X₁ = Credit Obtained (in naira)
- X₂ = Age (years)
- X₃ = Sex (Male= 1; 0 otherwise)
- X₄ = Marital Status (Married = 1; 0 otherwise)
- X₅ = Household Size (Number)
- X₆ = Formal Education (years)
- X₇ = Cooperative Experience (years)
- X₈ = Distance of the credit source (Km)
- U = Error Term

(iv) Identify the challenges militating against cooperatives in rendering these services to members.

Descriptive statistics were used to identify the challenges militating against cooperatives in rendering services to member. The descriptive tools to be used were mean and Likert Scale.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1: Socio-Economic Characteristics of the Respondents

Variables	Frequency	Percentage	Mean
Sex			
Male	60	50.0	
Female	60	50.0	
Age (years)			40.16 years
20-30	27	22.5	
31-40	45	37.5	
41-50	32	26.7	
>50	16	13.3	
Educational Level			
No formal education	12	10.0	
Primary education	18	15.0	
Secondary education	49	40.8	
Tertiary education	41	34.2	
Marital Status			
Single	6	5.0	
Married	99	82.5	
Divorce	3	2.5	
Widowed	5	4.2	
Widower	7	5.8	
Household Size (person)			7
1 - 4	23	19.2	
5 - 8	77	64.2	
9 - 12	14	11.7	
>12	6	5.0	
Occupation			
Trader	55	45.8	
Civil service	35	29.2	
Artisan	30	25.0	
Types of Cooperatives			
CTCS	78	65.0	
Multipurpose Cooperative society	5	4.2	
Others	37	30.8	
Type of Service Rendered			
Loan	57	47.5	

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Marketing Service	2	1.7	
Purpose of Coop. Soc.			
All service	61	50.8	
Single Purpose	56	46.7	
Multi-Purpose	64	53.3	
Total	120	100	

Source: Field Survey, 2020

Findings revealed that Socio-Economic Characteristics (SEC) usually refers to components of economic and social status that distinguish and characterize people. Indicators of SEC are meant to reflect access to social and economic resources that may vary overtime (Duncan *et al.*, 2002) and by households.

Data in Table 1 showed that both male (50.0%) and female (50.0%) were equally represented in the study. The result showed that male household heads and female heads are in the study area. This can be attributed to the predominance of the male and female headed households in cooperative activities in rural and urban areas of Nigeria.

According to age distribution the results from the study shows that majority of the respondents in the study area (37.5%) are between 31 and 40 years of age. This implied that middle age respondents dominated the study area. Respondents in this age group constitute the very energetic youth and are likely to work effectively to increase their outputs with an average age of 40.16 years. The result also revealed that 86.7% of the respondents are between the ages of 30 to 50 years. This implies that most of the respondents are in their active and agile ages which will enhance their performance in cooperative activities and thereby generate income for them.

Finding summarizes the educational status of the respondents, that just 10.0% of the respondents are not literates. Such respondents did not receive any form of formal education and are likely to have inadequate knowledge on loan acquisition and management, thereby making them unable to utilize the loans given to them properly thereby reducing their output. Majority of the households (90%) in the study area are literate This result follow in line with the work of Adesanoye and Okunmadewa (2007) in which majority of the respondents were literate with about 90 percent. In terms of education 15.0% of the respondents in the study area ended their education in the primary school while majority 40.8% of the respondents have secondary education and 34.2% of the respondents got to the Tertiary level. This implies that education is vital for cooperative development. It serves as motivation to enhance knowledge of the cooperative officers about cooperative activities.

Distribution of the respondents by marital status in the study area revealed that majority of the respondents (82.5%) are married and the remaining (17.5%) are unmarried (i.e single, divorced or widow). This result shows that most of the respondents in the study area are married and these married respondents are likely to spend much of their income on their families. The predominance of married people in the study area may be attributed to the prevalence of early marriages or the ideals of the customs and traditions that are held in high esteem.

The household size distribution of the rural households revealed that majority 64.2% of the households in the study area have a family size between 5 and 8 members' and 11.7% of the respondents have family size between 9 and 12 members with an average family size of about 7 members per household. This shows that a greater percentage of the respondents have fairly large family sizes and this could likely raise their total household expenses and negatively affect their ability to access loan. On the other hand, the large sizes of the families could serve as a source of labour which will increase the output of the respondents and hence positively affect the respondents' household income.

The findings revealed the frequency distribution of occupations of the respondents in the study area to be trading, civil service and artisans. Majority (45.8%) of the respondents are traders, with 29.2% in the civil service and 25.0% are artisan. This implied that there was no regular distribution of occupation among the respondents but trading was the most common occupation among the respondents in the study area.

Majority (65.0%) of the cooperatives members are under the Credit and Thrift Cooperative Societies, while (30.8%) of the respondents are members of other cooperative societies with only 4.2% under Cooperative Multi-Purpose Societies. This implies that more of the cooperatives in the study area are only based on credit and thriftiness which encourages savings pattern among members and make credit available to their members.

The result revealed in Table 4.8 showed that majority of the cooperative societies (50.8%) were offering all type of services from marketing to credit facilities to their members while other cooperatives (47.5%) render credit services to their members.

The result of analysis which shows that 53.3% of the cooperative societies were serving a range of multipurpose from marketing, to credit and procurement of inputs and so on while 46.7% only serve a single purpose which is mainly loan service. This implies that cooperatives that are multipurpose provide loan service, marketing and other functions in cooperative to their members.

Effect of Motivation on Cooperative Performance

The descriptive statistics of 5 point scale analysis was used to analyse the perceived effect of motivation on cooperative. Table 2 shows the distribution with threshold of 3.0, it was revealed that relationships with peers have really contributed to cooperative performance in the study area, as it is indicated in the grand mean ($x = 4.62$) which is great than the standard mean of 3.00. Therefore, motivation of cooperative society have really impacted positive contributions to cooperative performance. Some of these motivations include, assistance from the government and any other bodies (3.87); number in the management team (3.78); staff training/development programs (3.73); working conditions (3.28); promotion in the organization (3.21) and opportunity for advancement (3.13).

Table 2: Distribution of Effect of Motivation on Cooperative Performance

Factors	Mean (\bar{x})	Decision
Number in the Management Team	3.7750	Agree
Promotion in the Organization	3.2083	Agree
Staff training/Development Programs	3.7333	Agree
Is there any assistance from the government or any other bodies	3.8667	Agree
Opportunity for Advancement	3.1250	Agree
Appreciation for Work Done	2.6417	Disagree
Salary/Wages	2.6333	Disagree
Working Conditions	3.2750	Agree
Relationships with Peers	4.6167	Agree

Source: Field Survey data, 2020. Likert-Rating: $< 3.0 = \text{Disagree}$, $\geq 3.0 = \text{Agree}$

Impact of Cooperative Services on Members' Outputs

Data in Table 3 shows the regression estimates on the impact of cooperative services received by members from the cooperative on their outputs. It has an R^2 value of 0.512 which implies that about 51.2% of the variation in the dependent variable is caused by the independent variables included in the model while the other remaining 39.8% might be due to error in specification and exclusion of other factors in the model. The F statistics is significant at 1% which implies that the variables included adequately described the dependent variable. Of the seven variables that were included, two were found to significantly affect the performance (Outputs) of members. The coefficient of credit obtained is significant at 10% and has a direct influence on the total performance of the farmers. Credit availability influences production positively since it empowers the members to build up stock over time. The coefficient of household size is significant at 10% and has effect on the cooperative members' outputs. Credit and household size are needed more to enhance cooperative members' output in the area.

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Table 3: Regression Estimate for Impact of Cooperative Services on Members' Outputs

Variable Code and Name	Reg. Coefficient	Standard Error	T-value
(β_0) (Constant)	9.912	5.251	1.887*
(X1) Credit Obtained	0.018	0.034	1.817*
(X2) Age	1.355	10.090	0.134
(X3) Sex	-7.343	178.465	-0.041
(X4) Marital status	-4.973	238.423	-0.021
(X5) Household size	1.836	2.916	1.696*
(X6) Formal education	3.699	16.699	0.222
(X7) Cooperative experience	-1.778	2.277	-0.781
R²	0.512		
Adjusted R²	0.450		
F-value	4.194***		

Source: Field Survey, 2020 *** sig. at 1% level, * sig. at 10% level

Challenges Militating Against Cooperatives in Rendering these Services

As shown in Table 4 the cooperative members agreed that the following challenges militated against the cooperative societies in rendering services to cooperative members: Inadequate capital (65.0%); High cost of obtaining farm inputs (51.7%); inadequate infrastructure (64.2%) and inadequate capacity building/training (53.3%). The result revealed that inadequate capital ranked first. This implies that inadequate capital hinders job motivation in monetary terms in area of incentives, fringe benefit, Christmas or Leave bonus and in sending the cooperative officers for training, seminars and workshops.

Table 4: Distribution of challenges militating against cooperative rendering services

Challenges	Frequency (n=120)	Percentage (%)	Rank
Inadequate capital	78	65.0	1 st
High cost of obtaining farm inputs	62	51.7	4 th
Inadequate infrastructure	77	64.2	2 nd
Corruption	44	36.7	5 th
Poor leadership	23	19.2	9 th
Poor monitoring and evaluation	10	8.3	10 th
Inadequate capacity building/training	64	53.3	3 rd
Lack of transparency	34	28.3	6 th
Undemocratic tendencies	28	23.3	7 th
Poor supervision and regulation from agency in charge of cooperative	26	21.7	8 th

Source: Field Survey Data, 2020

CONCLUSION

The study concludes that cooperative society membership is being joined by both male and female whose average age was 40.16 years and are mostly in their active age, they are educated and can read and write. The cooperative members are married with a fairly large household size of 7 persons per households and they are traders who are in the Credit and Thrift Cooperative Societies. The cooperative societies in the area offers all type of services from marketing to credit facilities to their members and serves a multipurpose from marketing, to credit and procurement of inputs. The relationships with peers, assistance from the government and any other bodies, number in the management team, staff training/development programs, working conditions and promotion in the organization all motivates cooperative performance in the study area. Credit is needed more to enhance cooperative members' output in the area. Challenges militating against the cooperative societies in rendering services to cooperative members are inadequate capital, high cost of obtaining farm inputs, inadequate infrastructure and inadequate capacity building/training.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The result from the analysis in this study is being discussed and the following recommendations are given:

- (i) People should be encouraged and enlightened to form and join cooperative society. The ministry responsible for cooperative should give orientation to people on the benefits and need of obtaining cooperative membership which will enable them access credit to increase output.
- (ii) Stake holders in cooperative societies need to increase management training programmes so as to increase the performance level of cooperative societies.
- (ii) Training and skills acquisition programmes should be organized for members as often as necessary so as to ensure that they possess the technical, business management and personal entrepreneurial skills, and all other relevant skills to their respective businesses.

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